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Acceptance Letter

Author(s) Name	Amit Sharma, Prof. Ambrish Pandey, Prof. Rajendrakumar Anayath
Paper Title	Study of Colour Shift due to Aqueous Coating on various Coated Substrate in Offset Printing

Dear Author(s)

We are pleased to inform you that your paper submitted for publishing in **Nanotechnology Perceptions** ISSN: 1660-6795, E-ISSN: 2235-2074 has been **accepted** based on the recommendations provided by the assigned reviewers. By this mail you are requested to proceed with the publication formalities.

Paper Status:	Accepted	Accepted after changes	Rejected
Please prepare camera ready paper as per Nanotechnology Perceptions paper template format. If you had taken anypart/figure/table from any other research paper then kindly mention it in References.			

Kindly complete all the required formalities (Camera Ready and Copyright) as soon as possible, as failing to which your paper may be subjected to rejection. After completing all formalities your manuscript will be published in the current issue, 2024.

Nanotechnology Perceptions Team congratulates you for this achievement.

Regards

Editorial Team
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